

EVOLUTION OF PREDICTIVE ANALYSIS USING GPT OPENAI MODELS

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Abstract: Data analysis, particularly predictive analysis, has seen significant development with the emergence of modern LLMs, especially the latest GPT models. Nowadays, Generative AI is a turning point in modern industry. Many new LLMs have been available during the last several years, but an essential case is how these models are changing: what is the direction of evolution, and what can we expect from Gen AI shortly?

This study analyses different aspects of the evolution of predictive analysis systems using different LLMs: GPT 3.5 turbo, GPT-4, GPT-4o, GPT-4o1 OpenAI GPT o1.

This report includes comparative studies of predictive analysis for construction structures conducted using a comparative reference framework with different GPT models, reaching GPT-4o and GPT o1. The accuracy of the analysis on identical cases is compared. The study also compares the cost and performance of the different models. Current research will be useful for scientists, researchers, industry engineers, and businesses to estimate the cost and effectiveness of the GenAI solutions that they are going to implement and choose the right LLM for their cases and

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1. Introduction

One of the main points in the new era of Generative AI, LLMs, and AI as a service, in general, is how models are changing and what the main trends in the evolution of large language models are. This paper is focused preliminary on the OpenAI GPT models, but the trend is similar for many other LLMs. The research covers the accuracy of the models and the learning curve during the adoption of GenAI technologies. The last point has to do with how easily users learn how to interact with AI.

The first OpenAI LLM generations up to GPT-3.5 focus on routine tasks. The accuracy is not very good, but these models are good for essential customer integration.

GPT-4.0 models provide options for perfect refining AI-powered customer interactions. These models are very accurate and have good interaction capabilities.

GPT-4o models bring more advanced language processing and adaptive learning. These models have no better accuracy than GPT-4.0 in a specific completion request, but they have superior capabilities to support complex business operations [2]

The current statistics on the preciseness of the OpenAI GPT models are relevant for specific cases analyzed for specific cases like problem-solving at the International Mathematical Olympiad (IMO)

Fig. 1 and Table 1 compare different GPT models (GPT-3.5 and the later models). Results demonstrated from GPT-4 models are the most accurate (in the case of mathematical tasks) compared to the other Open AI models (including also the latest one).

Fig.1. Accuracy Comparison Across GPT Model Versions [3]

Table 1. OpenAI Foundation GPT models The evolution of accuracy for OpenAI's language models

Model Version	Release Date	Accuracy in Specific Tasks	Notable Observations
GPT-1	June 2018	Not specified	Introduced the generative pre-training approach, setting the foundation for subsequent models.
GPT-2	February 2019	Not specified	Demonstrated significant improvements in text generation but raised concerns about potential misuse due to its ability to generate coherent and contextually relevant text.
GPT-3	June 2020	Not specified	Showed substantial advancements in natural language understanding and generation, capable of performing a wide range of tasks without task-specific training.
GPT-3.5	2022	~53%	Achieved approximately 53% accuracy in specific tasks, such as physiology and pharmacology assessments.
GPT-4	March 2023	97.6% (initially) 95.2% (updated)	Initially achieved 97.6% accuracy in identifying prime numbers. However, by June 2023, this accuracy declined to 2.4% for the same task, indicating variability in performance over time.
GPT-4o	May 2024	86%	Achieved 86% accuracy in physiology and pharmacology assessments, marking a notable improvement from earlier versions.
GPT-4o1 Preview	October 2024	86%	Maintained the improvements seen in GPT-4o, with 86% accuracy in specific assessments.
OpenAI o1	September 2024	83% (IMO qualifier)	In a qualifying exam for the International Mathematical Olympiad (IMO), o1 correctly solved 83% of problems, significantly outperforming GPT-4o's 13% accuracy on the same task.

Results from the general comparison are related to a benchmark framework used for the evaluation of LLMs. This framework includes:

- Quantitative Evaluation
- Human evaluation
- Computational Resource Analysis

- Robustness Testing (test on generalization)
- Longitudinal analysis (performance over time and model drift)

Details on the methods to evaluate and compare LLMs will be explained later in this paper.

It is important to get insights about the targets for each of the GPT models to understand why the accuracy has changed and is not only in one direction. Some of the newer GPT models are observed to have lower accuracy compared to some older ones. The directions of development for different GPT LLMs are described in Figure 2.

Fig.2. GPT models, including their main specifics [4]

Another important metric for LLMs is related to ease of prompting. The adoption of AI, and especially AI as a service, depends on how easily organizations can use these technologies.

Table 2. Metrics of Comparison. Ease of Prompting for Different GPT models.[5]

Metric	GPT-3	GPT-3.5	GPT-4	GPT-4o	GPT-4o1	OpenAI o1
Instruction Following	70%	85%	95%	88%	90%	92%
Few-shot Learning Ability	Medium	High	Very High	High	Very High	Very High
Tolerance to Ambiguity	Low	Medium	High	Medium	High	Medium
Response Coherence	Medium	High	Very High	High	Very High	Very High
Prompt Robustness	Medium	High	Very High	Medium	High	High
Overall Ease of Prompting	65%	80%	90%	85%	88%	86%

The main KPIs include:

- Instructions Following: measures the ability of the models to interpret detailed or ambiguous instructions
- Few-shot Learning Ability: shows how well the model adapts to examples provided in the prompt.
- Tolerance to Ambiguity: this metric demonstrates how well the model handles unclear and imprecise prompts.
- Response Coherence: considers how logically consistent and fluent the output is relative to the prompt

- Prompt Robustness: shows how well the model deals with noisy or suboptimal prompts.
- Overall Ease of Prompting: A combined score reflecting all the above factors

The last essential group of metrics that is needed to compare OpenAI LLMs is related to the pricing. Table 3 demonstrates the current pricing (December 2024) for different OpenAI GPT models

Table 3. OpenAI Foundation GPT models pricing

Model	Context Window (tokens)	Pricing
GPT-3	4K	\$0.02 per 1K tokens
GPT-3.5	16K	\$0.015 per 1K tokens
GPT-4	8K	\$0.03 per 1K tokens
GPT-4o	128K	\$0.005 per 1K input tokens; \$0.015 per 1K output tokens
GPT-4o mini	128K	\$0.00015 per 1K input tokens; \$0.0006 per 1K output tokens
OpenAI o1	128K	\$0.015 per 1K input tokens; \$0.06 per 1K output tokens
OpenAI o1-min	128K	80% cheaper than OpenAI o1

The main KPIs are described below:

- Context Window: this parameter is related to the maximum number of tokens used for the model in a single interaction.
- Pricing: Reflects the cost per 1,000 tokens processed, with distinctions between input and output tokens for certain models.

LLMs, and especially OpenAI GPT models, can be applied to various kinds of analysis.

- Descriptive analysis
- Diagnostic analysis
- Predictive analysis
- Prescriptive analysis

Descriptive analysis focuses on examining and summarizing data to provide insights into the current state of a specific situation. This type of analysis helps to interpret, visualize, and summarize data, often serving as a foundation for other analytical approaches. It is particularly well-suited for Computer Vision, as it can interpret and convey the meaning of images or videos. While it can leverage various technologies, using AI-powered solutions makes extracting metadata from diverse types of digital content significantly more efficient and manageable.

Diagnostic analysis is analyzing the root causes of something that happens (for example, construction failure). Descriptive metadata from images and videos can be critical in explaining why something (events, behaviors, outcomes) happened. It works together with descriptive analysis to get information describing the case and find the main reason for having a specific situation.

Predictive analysis focuses on forecasting future events or outcomes by leveraging various data inputs. This type of analysis can be enhanced with AI, either as a standalone analytical solution or through a hybrid approach integrating AI elements. Predictive analysis can be implemented using various Large Language Models (LLMs) such as GPT, DALL-E, DAVINCI, and WHISPER. One major scenario is related to the analysis of images and video content, where other AI technologies like Computer Vision often

play a critical role in extracting the necessary information to serve as input for predictive analysis. The predictions are then generated using suitable LLMs that analyze the metadata derived from Computer Vision processes. This scenario will be discussed later in chapter 3 of the paper.

Prescriptive analysis provides actionable recommendations for future decisions based on the outcomes of predictive analysis. It leverages statistical algorithms, machine learning techniques, and other AI-driven solutions to determine the optimal next steps in a given situation.

This research is focused on how different GPT models perform in scenarios related to predictive analysis. The comparison covers some of the latest GPT models, included in real-life scenarios for structure maintenance and prediction.

The next chapter explains the prerequisites to design and implement the PoC used for the experimental research.

2. Prerequisites and means for solving the problem

This paper covers the following areas:

- Design and implementation of Predictive Analysis based on Computer Vision using OpenAI
- Democratization of the implementation of flows, providing Predictive Analysis with OpenAI and Power Automate (Low Code/No Code)
- Analyze the results (preciseness and correctness, ease of prompting, and price) based on sample data (photos of structures and construction schema).
- Options to optimize the cost and performance
- A reference comparison between general performance, ease of use, and pricing metrics and the specific one for scenarios with predictive analysis is needed to analyze if general trends are valid for prediction use cases.

The current research uses a reference framework to implement solutions with a short time to market, analyze cases from images and video, and provide predictive analysis to implement predictive maintenance and decrease the overall maintenance cost for different structures in the construction industry.

The overall schema explaining different types of analysis and related AI technologies, Computer Vision, and Open AI is demonstrated in Fig.3

Fig. 3. Implementation of different types of analysis using Computer Vision, Open AI – general dependencies

2.1 Areas of Optimization for Solutions Using AI as a Service

Modern solutions stay more integrated with AI services that are used as a service. This approach makes the performance and cost optimization more complex and challenging. It is not enough to know the best-performing services in a sandbox environment.

Optimization of analysis is considered in three primary directions:

- 1) Improving the preciseness
- 2) Performance optimization
- 3) Cost optimization

The first is mainly related to solution design, decomposition, and a combination of analysis based on different AI-related technologies. The general performance uses, in addition to architectural patterns and a mixture of AI and Analytics technologies, to provide faster and cheaper solutions on a scale. In this aspect, the best-performing standalone AI services are not always components of the best-performing solution, solving specific problems. LLM Optimization directions are shown in Fig. 4.

This article's primary focus is on performance metrics related to image analysis for Predictive Analysis for Construction using OpenAI with Computer Vision, described in [7]. The concept is also applicable to a variety of different cases from different domains.

Fig. 4.. LLM Optimization stages [8]

The research covered a comparison between different OpenAI GPT models, working in a solution for predictive analytics based on OpenAI and Computer Vision, including RAG and fine-tuning. Details on the experimental setup are explained in the next chapter of this paper.

3. Solution of the examined problem

The main focus is on solving similar cases for Predictive Analysis for Construction using OpenAI with Computer Vision. Generative AI needs a very well-described case to generate a valuable answer. In the experimental solutions,

The subject of the research is to analyze the effect of using different concepts for improvement of performance and cost efficiency for image analysis, based on Open AI multi-modal LLMs (GPT-4, GPT-4o, GPT-4o1). GPT-3.5 is not applicable because it doesn't support image analysis.

The experimental environment uses configuration with GPT, Computer Vision, and Promptly.ai [9], RAG, and fine-tuning.

3.1 Implementation of Analysis based on Computer Vision and OpenAI/ChatGPT

The experimental setup includes a module for case decompositions based on Digital Twins (DT) on Azure (Azure Digital Twins / ADT). ADT is used to manage the overall context from the observed solution, decompose the case, and unify the analysis case, converting it from domain-specific to domain-agnostic subcases suitable for LLM analysis.

One high-level schema of the solution is presented in Fig. 5

Fig.5. Experimental Setup: Predictive analysis using Image Analysis with Computer Vision Open AI LLM

The coordination service helps create and ask questions that clarify the search and allow the OpenAI service to provide the right solution. Digital Twins (DT) is a part of the solution that can be skipped if there is no decomposition of complex tasks. The coordination service is based on Low-code/No-code: Power Platform (Power Automate) for PoC. For analysis, sample data of rusty construction components from the USA, like the one in Fig. 6 :

Fig.6. Sample image of steel construction with corrosion

4. Results and discussion

In this paper, metrics related to the experimental project PoC are added and realized using Microsoft Azure, OpenAI, ten videos, and 2000 experimental images.

Test experiments are provided by deploying the test environment and LLM models in the Central Sweden Azure Region. The existence of all components in the same cloud region minimizes the variations in the latency based on the connectivity between different solution components (except Power Automate). Detailed results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. OpenAI Foundation GPT models pricing

LLM	AI Vision	images	videos	success rate	time image[s]	time video[s]	RAG
GPT-4	no	2000	10	98.1%	540	790	no
GPT-4	no	2000	10	98.1%	298	710	yes
GPT-4	yes	2000	10	99.2%	540	780	no
GPT-4	yes	2000	10	99.2%	298	661	yes
GPT-4o	no	2000	10	98.2	278	410	no
GPT-4o	no	2000	10	98.2	188	340	yes
GPT-4o	yes	2000	10	99.4	278	399	no
GPT-4o	yes	2000	10	99.4	188	320	yes
GPT-4o1	no	2000	10	99.2	274	408	no
GPT-4o1	no	2000	10	99.5	187	338	yes
GPT-4o1	yes	2000	10	99.6	274	396	no
GPT-4o1	yes	2000	10	99.6	187	317	yes

5. Conclusions

The provided experiments demonstrate a list of dependencies and trends, explained below:

Predictive analysis can effectively use Open AI and AI-based image analysis to solve cases related to construction predictive maintenance.

Azure AI Vision for object detection provides relatively small additional precision, increasing the correctness of the description by up to 2-3%, but it has a higher impact on overall performance and cost reduction related to image analysis with LLM.

The overall analysis offered by automation solutions can effectively solve complex cases even on the PoC level using both custom and Low-Code/No-Code solutions. The approach is domain-agnostic and can be used in different business domains.

Cost and performance optimization rely on many factors. It depends on the specific LLM, but on a more significant level, and it can be improved up to several times using prompt optimization, Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG), and fine tuning, especially for the analysis of complex images and videos.

The cheapest implementation is based on GPT-4o, but the best-performing solution is based on GPT-4o1, despite the fact that the in-sandbox GPT-4 performs better than other GPT models.

6. Future work:

Research will be extended based on more complex cases and improved MML models. The major focus will be to propose the best framework, such as LLM models and solution design, for real-life prediction and maintenance cases related to manufacturing systems.

8. References

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